

case of PDM, upto 250 mg of substance dissolved in water (30 ml) was treated with 5 N sulphuric acid (10 ml) and isopropyl alcohol (10 ml), cooled to 15° and then titrated with cerium(IV). The end-point was indicated by the complete disappearance of the red colour.

Application of the method: Thirty tablets containing MH, PDM or PPP were crushed to a fine powder. A suitable amount of the powder was weighed accurately, dissolved in water and filtered through a quantitative filter paper. The final volume of the filtrate was adjusted to 40 ml as above and the drug content determined by the above procedure. For the analysis of injection solutions, the requisite volume of the injection solutions were transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with water. The drug content of the solution was determined as above.

Results and Discussion

Phenothiazines react with cerium(IV) in acid medium undergoing a one-electron reversible oxidation to a red coloured radical cation, which is irreversibly oxidised to a colourless sulphoxide with the loss of one more electron according to the following mechanism¹¹:

MH, R₁ = CH₃, C₆H₅, NCH₃, R₂ = H, X = hydrochloride
 PDM, R₁ = (CH₃)₂NC₆H₄NCH₃, R₂ = H, X = dimalonate
 PPP, R₁ = (CH₃)₂N(CH₃)₂, R₂ = COCH₂CH₃, X = phosphate

Effect of acidity, temperature and isopropanol: Preliminary investigations show that accurate results are obtained in an overall sulphuric acid concentrations of 0.5–3.5 N for PPP and 0.5–2.5 N for MH at room temperature. In the titration of PDM, addition of 15–30% (v/v) isopropanol and a lowering of temperature to 15 ± 5° are necessary to achieve stoichiometric results in 0.5–3.0 N sulphuric acid. The relative error does not exceed ± 1.2%.

Effect of pill additives: In order to assess the possible analytical applications of the method, the

effect of various pill additives that often accompany the psychotropic drugs in pharmaceutical preparations were studied. It has been found that there is no interference from 30-fold excess of talc, magnesium stearate, sodium citrate and dextrose. A 20-fold excess of starch and 10-fold excess of gelatin also do not interfere.

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Comparison of Co-solvent Effects on Solvent Sublation and Bubble Aeration of Hydrophobic Organics from Aqueous Solutions

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DIFFUSED bubble aeration and solvent sublation are two processes capable of removing trace hydrophobic organics from aqueous solutions using air bubbles. In the latter process, materials are transported both in the adsorbed phase on the air bubble surface as well as in the interior of the air bubbles and deposited in an overlying immiscible organic solvent like mineral oil, while in the former process no immiscible layer is present over the water column and hence only the material transported in the interior of the bubbles are removed from the aqueous phase¹. The success of conventional bubble aeration depends solely on the volatility of the hydrophobic. On the other hand, sublation only requires that the hydrophobic prefer the air-water interface of the bubbles; hence, partly

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volatile hydrophobics will be transported both in the adsorbed phase as well as in the vapor phase of the air bubbles. The driving force for sublation is that by aggregating at the air—water interface of air bubbles, the hydrophobic organic will decrease its area exposed to the water and thereby its free energy. The molecule is then said to be 'loosely sorbed' at the air—water interface since the free energy involved in such a process is very small (in the range 10^{-14} – 10^{-15} erg per molecule). Tall, narrow water columns, very small bubbles (of dia <0.5 mm) and low Reynold's number for the bubbles are prime requisites for a successful sublation process.

Several reports have appeared recently in the literature on the use of solvent sublation for the removal of hydrophobic organics from water²⁻¹⁰. It has also been reported that co-solutes like ethanol can effect the sublation process both in a negative as well as a positive sense^{3,5-9}. This paper describes the comparison of the effects of ethanol on the solvent sublation and simple aeration of a typical hydrophobic organic, viz., *p*-dichlorobenzene (DCB) from aqueous solution.

Experimental

The apparatus used for sublation as well as aeration was described in our earlier work^{2,8,10}. Briefly, it was a 100 cm tall Pyrex glass column of 5 cm outer diameter. The aqueous volume was 1785 ml in all the experiments and the organic solvent (mineral oil) volume for sublation was 50 ml. The aeration runs were made without any mineral oil on top of the aqueous section. Saturated aqueous solutions of 1,4-dichlorobenzene (Fisher), and ethanol (Fisher) were used. The mineral oil used was of U.S.P. grade (Fisher).

The experimental procedures were exactly as described earlier^{2,8}. The air flow rate used was 1.0 ml s^{-1} in all the experiments. A hexane extraction technique⁹ was used to determine the DCB concentration in the aqueous phase. A Hewlett—Packard 5890 gas chromatograph with a nickel-63 electron capture detector was used for the analysis of DCB in the hexane extract. The column used was a 12 m HP-530 μ series capillary column of 0.20 mm internal diameter and coated with methyl-silicone OV-1. The injector, oven and detector temperatures were 200, 75 and 350°, respectively. Prepurified nitrogen at 37 ml min^{-1} flow rate was used as the carrier gas. A HP 3392A computing integrator was used to record and integrate the chromatograms.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results are reported as concentration changes in the aqueous phase with time since the process is a non-steady state batch one. These are shown in Fig. 1 for conventional aeration (without any mineral oil) and in Fig. 2 for solvent

sublation. The mole fractions of ethanol used were 2×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-3} and 2×10^{-2} in both sets of experiments and compared with the runs without any ethanol as co-solvent.

It is evident from Figs. 1 and 2 that the effects of low mole fractions of ethanol are more pronounced for sublation than for aeration. Low concentrations of ethanol (mole fractions less than 0.002) decrease the surface tension of water and hence bubble size is decreased. This increases the interfacial area per unit volume of air and also increases the bubble/water contact time, both of which would enhance sublation efficiency^{6,8,9}. The effects of increased solubility of DCB as a result of the presence of ethanol is apparently more than overwhelmed by the decreased bubble size in the column so far as sublation is concerned. On the other hand, the effects of decreased bubble size do not seem to improve the performance of aeration, whereas the effect of increased solubility is more than apparent as evidenced by decreased aeration rate constants even at low ethanol mole fractions. The effects of larger concentrations of ethanol (mole fractions 0.02 and larger) appear to be the same in both cases. At such ethanol concentrations, the increased solubility of DCB in ethanol—water mixtures seem to predominate and hence both sublation as well as aeration rate constants are reduced.

Indeed, theoretical models for the two processes predict these effects, as is shown here. Clarke and

Fig. 1. Aeration of 1,4-DCB (aq. vol.=1785 ml, air flow rate= 1.0 ml s^{-1}) 1(Δ) 0.000 g (5.66×10^{-3}), 2(\blacktriangle) 0.000 g (6.21×10^{-3}), 3(\bullet) 0.002 (4.58×10^{-3}), and 4(\circ) 0.02 (3.85×10^{-3}) xEtOH ($k, \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Fig. 2. Solvent sublation of 1,4-DCB (mineral oil vol.=50 ml, aq. vol.=1785 ml, air flow rate=1.0 ml s⁻¹; 1(Δ) 0.000 0 (1.01 × 10⁻⁴), 2(O) 0.000 2 (1.07 × 10⁻⁴), 3(●) 0.002 (1.28 × 10⁻⁴), and 4(▲) 0.02 (0.96 × 10⁻⁴) x EtOH (h, s⁻¹).

Wilson¹ proposed the following equation for the first order rate constant of simple aeration,

$$k(\text{aer}) = \frac{Q_a H}{V_w} \left[1 - \exp\left\{ \frac{-3k_w^s h}{r u} \right\} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, Q_a = air flow rate ml s⁻¹, H = Henry's constant which describes the extent of partitioning into the interior of an air bubble (dimensionless), V_w = total aqueous volume (ml), r = average bubble radius (cm), k_w^s = boundary layer mass transfer coefficient for transfer of hydrophobic from the aqueous phase into the interior of the bubble via volatilisation (cm s⁻¹), h = height of the aqueous column (cm), and u = bubble rise velocity (cm s⁻¹). A similar equation was obtained by Valsaraj *et al.*⁸ for the first order rate constant in sublation,

$$k(\text{sub}) = \frac{Q_a}{V_w} \left(H + \frac{3}{r} K \right) \left[1 - \exp\left\{ \frac{-k_w^s h}{\left(\frac{rH}{3} + K \right) u} \right\} \right] \quad (2)$$

where, K = linearised Langmuir isotherm constant which gives the extent of adsorption of the hydrophobic at the air-water interface of air bubbles (cm) and k_w^s = boundary layer mass transfer coefficient for simultaneous transfer of hydrophobics into the interior (via volatilisation) and onto the surface (via adsorption) of the air bubble (cm s⁻¹). Henry's

constant, H is given by⁸

$$H = \frac{P_{\text{vap}}}{RT} \cdot \frac{1}{C} \quad (3)$$

where, P_{vap} = vapor pressure of the hydrophobic (atm), R = gas constant, 0.080 25 dm³ atm K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, T = absolute temperature (K) and C = aqueous solubility of the hydrophobic, mol dm³. The adsorption constant, K is given by⁸

$$K = \frac{V_m}{NA_m} \exp\{-V_o/kT\} \quad (4)$$

where, adsorption energy,

$$V_o = 2 \gamma_{\text{aw}} \left[0.7 \left(\frac{\gamma_{\text{as}}}{\gamma_{\text{aw}}} \right)^{1/2} - 1 \right] A_m \quad (5)$$

and V_m = molar volume of the hydrophobic (cm³ mol⁻¹), A_m = area occupied by a hydrophobic molecule at the air-water interface (cm² mol⁻¹), N = Avogadro's constant and γ_{as} , γ_{aw} = surface tensions of hydrophobic solute and water, respectively (dyne cm⁻¹).

Using the procedure described by Clarke and Wilson¹, k_w^s for DCB was calculated to be 3.89 × 10⁻³ cm s⁻¹ for a bubble of radius 0.025 cm, a boundary layer thickness⁹ of 0.007 18 cm and a bubble rise velocity⁸ of 4.86 cm s⁻¹. The Henry's constant¹⁰ for DCB was 0.087. For the same bubble parameters, k_w^s for DCB was calculated to be 5.03 × 10⁻⁴ cm s⁻¹ as described by Valsaraj *et al.*⁸ and Huang *et al.*³. The other relevant parameters for DCB used in these calculations were as follows^{8,10}: $A_m = 50 \times 10^{-16}$ cm² mol⁻¹, $V_m = 133$ cm³ mol⁻¹, $\gamma_{\text{as}} = 32.9$ dyne cm⁻¹, $\gamma_{\text{aw}} = 72$ dyne cm⁻¹ and $D = 6 \times 10^{-6}$ cm² s⁻¹.

For a 100 cm tall aqueous column, these parameters result in values of the exponential functions in equations (1) and (2) of 6.77 × 10⁻⁵ and 1.7 × 10⁻⁴, respectively. Thus equations (1) and (2) reduce to

$$k(\text{aer}) = \frac{Q_a H}{V_w} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{and } k(\text{sub}) = \frac{Q_a}{V_w} \left(\frac{3K}{r} + H \right) \quad (6b)$$

The above results imply that under the experimental conditions (tall columns and small bubbles), the sublation rate constant is extremely sensitive to the bubble radius while aeration rate constant is not. Small concentrations of ethanol will decrease the value of both H (by increasing¹¹ C) and K (by decreasing¹² γ_{aw}) as shown in Table 1.

However, at low ethanol mole fractions, the decrease in K is more than compensated by decreasing r , thus increasing $3K/r$ in sublation and hence $k(\text{sub})$. But there is a limit to which r can be reduced by increasing ethanol concentration; and thereafter the decrease in K predominates resulting in reduced $k(\text{sub})$ values and makes sublation an ineffective process. On the other hand, for aeration experiments, since $k(\text{aer})$ depends only on the H

TABLE 1—VALUES OF HENRY'S CONSTANT AND ADSORPTION ISOTHERM CONSTANT OF DCB AT VARIOUS ETHANOL CONCENTRATIONS IN WATER

Ethanol mol fraction	Aqueous solubility of DCB ^a C (mg dm ⁻³)	Surface tension of water ^b γ _{aw} (dyne cm ⁻¹)	Henry's constant ^c H	Adsorption isotherm constant ^d K (cm)
0.000 0	80.00	72	0.087 0	4.47 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.000 2	80.16	70	0.086 7	3.09 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.002	81.60 ^o	68	0.085 2	2.13 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.02	97.60	54	0.071 2	1.70 × 10 ⁻⁵

^aC was calculated as given in Ref. 11; $\log(C/C_0) = 3.8 \times 10^{-6} C(\text{EtOH})$, where C_0 is the aqueous solubility of DCB in pure water (=80 mg dm⁻³) and $C(\text{EtOH})$ is the ethanol concentration in g m⁻³. ^bγ_{aw} obtained from Ref. 12. ^cVapor pressure of DCB=0.879 mm/Hg at 25°. ^dMolecular parameters used: $A_m = 50 \times 10^{-16}$ cm³ mol⁻¹, $V_m = 133$ cm³ mol⁻¹, $\phi = 0.7$.

value, whatever the ethanol concentration, reduced H value results in reduced $k(\text{aer})$ and hence even slight amounts of ethanol makes aeration an ineffective process. It is thus apparent that reduced bubble size and consequent increase in air-water interfacial area is more important for sublation than it is for aeration. This is not surprising since sublation is a surface chemical technique as explained in detail by Clarke and Wilson¹. The amount of material carried in the adsorbed and vapor phases of an average bubble (radius 0.025 cm) can be calculated as shown by Huang *et al.*³. These values for DCB turn out to be 38% for the adsorbed phase and 62% for the vapor phase. Experimental sublation and aeration rate constant (for the case of no ethanol) of DCB from Figs. 1 and 2 show that 57% is carried in the vapor phase and 43% in the adsorbed phase in fair agreement with the predicted values. DCB

can thus be considered a volatile hydrophobic compound.

These experiments are thus further proof for the 'loose sorption' of hydrophobics at the air-water interfaces which becomes noticeable only in sublation and not in aeration. Thus sublation is a definite improvement over conventional diffused aeration.

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